

PSYCHODIAGNOSTICS AND PSYCHOCORRECTION OF EMOTIONAL TENSION

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Abstract. This article specifically touches on the topic of psychodiagnostics and psychocorrection of emotional tension in pedagogical activity. Throughout the article, there are reasonable opinions and considerations within the subject area. The article was last mentioned giving conclusions and suggestions.

Keywords: pedagogical activity, emotional tension, psychodiagnostics, brain activity.

ПСИХОДИАГНОСТИКА И ПСИХОКОРРЕКЦИЯ ЭМОЦИОНАЛЬНОГО НАПРЯЖЕНИЯ

Аннотация. В данной статье специально затрагивается тема психодиагностики и психокоррекции эмоционального напряжения в педагогической деятельности. На протяжении всей статьи приводятся обоснованные мнения и соображения в рамках предметной области. В последний раз упоминалась статья с выводами и предложениями.

Ключевые слова: педагогическая деятельность, эмоциональное напряжение, психодиагностика, мозговая активность.

Emotional states, like other mental processes, are considered the result or product of brain activity. The main reason for the occurrence of emotional states is the changes, relationships, contacts, impressions taking place in nature and society. Changes, in turn, lead, firstly, to an acceleration or decrease in the life and activity of a person, and secondly, to the emergence or loss of certain needs in a person, and thirdly, to the destabilization of the functional states of the internal organs of a person. Unconditioned and conditioned reflexes serve as the basis of the most characteristic physiological processes for emotions, and their particular system occurs in the trunk of the large hemispheres of the brain and is strengthened at this place. While complex unconditioned reflexes are:

1) hemispherical subcutaneous cavities;

2) visual disturbances in the brain;

3) it is carried out through its centers, which transfer nerve excitations from the upper divisions of the brain to the vegetative system. The course of emotions in a person always occurs as a result of the unity (collaborative) activity of the pectoral centers with the cerebral cortex.

In modern times, the concept of "Health" is based on the concept of the World Organization for the preservation of Health, "the complete physical, mental, physical health of the body, which is not only the absence of diseases, but also the absence of physical defects." A disease is a condition characterized by a violation of human life activity, which leads to a decrease in the temporary or permanent functioning of the body. Of course, at the origin of the disease, the state of the organism, age, the presence or absence of comorbid diseases, how much microorganisms that call Disease fall into the body, the presence of hereditary predisposition, the reactivity of the

organism are important. Of course there are several conditions for longevity, and if a person complies with these conditions, the supreme goal that he sets himself is to set the stage for longevity. These include:

Improper nutrition. One of the factors that negatively affect health is considered improper, uncoordinated and irregular nutrition, causing disruption of the normal functioning of the body and the origin of various diseases Hypodynamia- (Greek-hypo-low, low, and dynamic-strength) insufficient muscle function is a decrease in contraction force, usually accompanied by constant sitting work, walking folding, transportation, agility, hypokinesia caused by a decrease in weight that falls on the muscles in general, i.e., a decrease in human activity of movement.

Movement and health. The main way to form a healthy lifestyle and prevent diseases is properly organized physical activity. As a result of the action, the activity of various organs and ridges of a person is normalized, and their disturbed activities are restored, their activity for mental and physical labor increases. Harmful habits: alcoholism - heavy drinking is the regular consumption of alcohol in excess of the norm, to the extent that some people harm their own health and ability to work, as well as the well-being of society. Smoking tobacco is one of the most harmful habits that seriously undermine a person's health. Nicotine has a temporary excitatory effect on the central and peripheral nervous system, increases arterial blood pressure, narrows small vessels; accelerates breathing, increases the juice of the digestive system. Along with nicotine, combustion products in tobacco smoke also poison the body. Therefore, it is also harmful for non-smokers to be in a smoked room. Smoke, which is a combustion product in its composition, reduces oxygen in the arterial blood when inhaled. It causes chronic bronchitis and pulmonary emphysema by affecting the mucous membrane of the bronchi. Addiction - (Greek-narke-numbness and mania - madness, anger, cheerfulness), bangilik, addiction-is a disease caused by the abuse of drugs and drugs with narcotic effects. The physical and mental state of a person with this disorder depends on the use of a narcotic substance that presses on the humorist. In the following two cases, one can get used to drugs:

Mental-emotional tensions are the main factors that negatively affect the health of people in the current period. The normal functioning of the human organism depends on what level of its psyche is. Any changes in psyche and mood directly affect the functioning of organs and systems. A person's mental crush, heartbreaking experiences and various negative events in life lead to tension. As a result of mental-emotional tension, hypertension, stenocardia and myocardial infarction in people, as well as mental disorders, obsession with harmful habits arise. In women, on the other hand, mental-emotional strains can cause extremely dangerous complications, especially during pregnancy, in its first 3 months. The improvement of the living of the population, the stabilization of social conditions are among the main conditions for the Prevention of mental-emotional tensions.

Lifestyle is a concept that involves a person's life, work, rest, etc., expressed in a specific society, environment. Its components include not only socio-political and productive activities, but also activity, socio-cultural activities in addition to production in time. Medical activity is also a form of it. In marriage, a person can fall into various negative impressions, adverse situations and conditions. These, in turn, force health and sedentary lifestyle to have full knowledge of wellness, educate the population's attitudes towards their own health, and promote medical knowledge. In conclusion, to have an understanding of the anti-health factors listed above, to

eliminate them, depends directly on each person himself. To do this, it is necessary to carry out explanatory work among the population on healthy living and what its components consist of. Of course, the main goal of pedagogical education is not only to educate young people, but also to provide education. Unhealthy lifestyle patterns (unemployment, under-maintenance, orphanhood, etc.) are responsible for the rapid and widespread spread of disease among young people. The increase in the incidence of chronic diseases among young people indicates that among them it is necessary to carry out a wide network of medical care: each student should know how to provide self-help, the organization of first aid, in extreme cases, emergency care. Emergencies of a natural, man-made, ecological nature cause an increase in injuries, injuries, poisoning, infectious diseases of various levels among young people, as well as in the population. In this case, it requires each person to quickly give self-help and mutual assistance. Only the fact that the population is healthy and educated makes a healthy contribution to the development and defense of the country. "Stress" is an English word that means tension, tension, pressure. In ordinary language, it is called depression. This can sometimes be a little opportunity, sometimes for a long time. In both cases, it causes harm to a person. That is, it causes a decrease in mental activity, an acceleration of the heart rate, an expansion of blood vessels, internal diseases - inflammations in the stomach. Another of the negative aspects of stress can brake the brain and reduce it to a meaningless thinking level. If a person often experiences depression, he falls into a state where he cannot talk to those around him. As a result of Stress, a person begins to give himself a low grade. In the end, he feels like he is alone and that he does not need his loved ones. Gradually, mental refreshment begins to disappear. How are the first signs of stress manifested? It has physiological and psychological types. Severe fear of something, unexpected car accidents or natural disasters, knowledge of the consequences of a disease in his body, sudden loss of a loved one cause physiological stress. Psychological stress is associated with the emotional state of a person. This is more due to conflicts between the mother-in-law-the bride, the couple or the mother and the child. Cases of separation from a lover who has been together for a long time or sudden dismissal also cause psychological stress. Both cases affect a person both in appearance and in the inner world, and, of course, there will be complications.

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